

N was added 3 wk after transplanting. The crop was harvested at maturity and grain and straw yields recorded. The grain and straw samples were digested in a diacid (HNO₃ + HClO₄ in 4:1 ratio) mixture and analyzed for K. Percent yield or K uptake was calculated:

$$\text{Percent yield or K uptake} = \frac{\text{yield or K uptake without K treatment}}{\text{yield or K uptake with applied K}} \times 100$$

Available K in soil was extracted using IN neutral ammonium acetate (1:5 soil: solution, 5 min shaking); 0.5 M sodium bicarbonate of pH 8.5 (1:20 soil: solution, 30 min shaking); Morgan's reagent 3% acetic acid + 10% sodium acetate of pH 4.8 (1:5 soil:solution, 5 min shaking); 1% citric acid (1: 10 soil:solution, 4 h shaking); Troug's reagent 0.002 N H₂SO₄ + 0.3% (NH₄)₂SO₄ with pH 3.0 (1:200 soil:solution, 30 min shaking); and boiling nitric acid (boiling 2.5 g soil in 25 ml IN HNO₃ for 10 min and 4 washings, each with 15 ml of 0.1N cold HNO₃ to make volume to 100 ml). Simple correlation coefficients were calculated for yield and K-uptake parameters with K indices (see table).

Grain yield varied from 8.5 to 44.5 g/pot in the control and 14.4 to 57.4 g/pot in treated pots. Total dry matter (grain + straw) yield varied from 25.4 to 102.1 g/pot and 38.8 to 107.5 g/pot in control and K-treated pots. Total K uptake by grain and straw ranged from 150 to 1,182 mg/pot in control and 280 to 1,373 mg/

Determining available K by different indices and their relation to rice plant parameters, Ludhiana, India.^a

	NH ₄ OAC	NaHCO ₃	Morgan	Citric acid	Troug	Nitric acid
	<i>Available K (ppm)</i>					
Range	26.3-179.9	50.0-270.1	62.5-325.0	29.9-195.1	9.8-220.1	533.0-2397.8
Mean	83.0 (±43.8)	127.7 (±64.5)	170.0 (±88.2)	101.0 (±53.0)	101.0 (±73.6)	1485.0 (±498.0)
	<i>Correlation coefficient (r-value)</i>					
Control grain yield	0.300	0.580**	0.438	0.398	0.335	0.340
Control dry matter yield	0.168	0.461*	0.300	0.263	0.163	0.198
Control grain K uptake	0.292	0.525*	0.437	0.374	0.345	0.331
Control dry matter K uptake	0.305	0.572**	0.444*	0.405	0.315	0.345
Percent grain yield	-0.234	0.085	0.044	-0.126	-0.205	0.080
Percent dry matter yield	-0.397	0.055	-0.100	-0.282	-0.330	0.092
Percent grain K uptake	-0.208	-0.032	-0.028	-0.156	-0.111	-0.023
Percent dry matter K uptake	-0.254	0.07	-0.605	-0.208	-0.235	0.150

^aSignificant at 5% (*) or 1% (**) levels; dry matter = grain + straw.

pot in K-treated pots. Grain yield varied from 59 to 98% and K uptake from 47 to 96%. Only in 6 soils was the response in yield or K uptake due to applied K above 20%. Results indicate that 2 to 41% of the yield obtained and 4 to 53% of K uptake could be attributed to applied K.

The correlation between control grain yield and control K uptake with K extracted by 0.5 M NaHCO₃ was highly significant ($r = 0.580^{**}$ and 0.572^{**}). Other methods related poorly with plant parameters. The prediction value (r^2) for the highest correlation of $r = 0.580$ was 33.6%. Probably the low response to

applied K in these soils resulted in low predictability for the indices. When different indices of K availability were related, we found that K extracted by 0.5 M NaHCO₃ was highly and significantly correlated with NH₄OAC extractable K ($r = 0.788^{**}$), suggesting that the former extractant can be satisfactorily used to estimate available K in the soils while also determining available P (0.5 M NaHCO₃ is an accepted method for estimating available P in these soils) in a single extraction. Soils with less than 72 ppm NaHCO₃-K are low in available K. □

Effect of N level on aged rice seedlings

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We studied tillering capacity, grain yield, and duration of IR20 at two seedling ages and different N levels in a randomized block design at TNRRI in 1983-84 winter.

Single 40- or 60-d-old seedlings were transplanted at 0 N, 100 kg N (50+25+25), 150 kg N (100+25+25), or 200 kg N (150+25+25)/ha as basal plus 2 top-dressings. Plots received 50 kg P and potash/ha basally.

Effect of seedling age and N level on IR20 duration, yield characters, and grain yield, Aduthurai, India.

Treatment N/ha)	Field duration (d)	Tillers/hill	Productive tillers/hill	Dry matter (t/ha)	Grain yield	
					kg/ha daily	t/ha
<i>40-d seedlings</i>						
0 N	103	5.8	5.3	7	26	2.7
50+25+25	110	8.5	8.1	16	37	4.1
100+25+25	111	9.4	8.9	17	39	4.4
150+25+25	111	9.8	8.1	19	41	4.5
<i>60-d seedlings</i>						
0 N	99	6.3	5.9	6	21	2.0
50+25+25	107	8.8	7.6	13	32	3.4
100+25+25	111	9.5	8.4	14	35	3.9
150+25+25	114	9.2	8.2	15	36	4.2
LSD (0.05)						
Treatments	1.5	1.2	1.2	2	3	0.3
Seedling age	ns	ns	ns	1	1	0.2
N	1.0	0.9	0.8	1	2	0.2

Primary tillers of 60-d-seedlings produced panicles in 21 d after transplanting, irrespective of N level, but there were only 2-3 tillers/hill.

Increasing N increased dry matter production, grain yield, and tillering at both seedling ages (see table).

At 200 kg N/ha, 60-d seedlings yielded grain on par with that at 150 kg N in 40-d seedlings. At 100+25+25 kg N, 60-d seedlings yielded on par with 40d seedlings at 50+25+25 kg N. Daily production increased with N application at a declining rate.

Main field duration of older seedlings was affected by N level, but there was no significant difference in field duration between seedling ages at higher N levels. The 40-d seedlings yielded better with less N. □

Impact of different soil moisture status on transplanted aman varieties

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We studied the effect of soil moisture status on rice yield in 1983 transplanted aman at BRRI. Soil moisture status was monitored in farmer fields from panicle initiation to crop maturity and 112 5-m² crop-cuts were collected from fields with different moisture status. Varietal reaction and grain yield, adjusted to 14% moisture content, were recorded,

With continuous standing water, BR11 yielded highest, 6.2 t/ha, which was 210% higher than yield with visible desiccation.

Yield of transplanted aman cultivars at different soil moisture levels, Gazipur, Bangladesh.^a

Soil moisture status	Average yield ^b (t/ha)								
	BR11 14	BR10 3	BR4 8	Pajam 30	Nizersail 23	Chandra sail 16	Chini- gura9 6	Kaligira 6	Binni 3
5-6 cm standing water	6.2 (210)	—	—	4.1 (128)	—	—	2.8 (47)	—	—
Saturated	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Moist but not saturated	4.9 (145)	—	3.6 (33)	3.5 (94)	—	—	—	—	—
Hair-like cracks	3.9 (95)	4.6 (31)	—	2.8 (56)	2.4 (50)	2.9 (61)	2.6 (36)	1.9 (28)	—
Visible cracks	—	—	3.0 (11)	2.6 (44)	2.2 (38)	2.3 (28)	—	—	—
Visible desiccation	2.0	3.5	2.7	1.8	1.6	1.8	1.9	1.5	1.2
Av	3.9	3.9	3.2	2.8	1.8	2.2	2.3	1.7	1.2

^aFigures under each variety name indicate the number of samples. Values in parentheses in each column indicate percent yield increase over the yield with visible desiccation.

BR10 and BR11 yielded an average 3.9 t/ha (see table). BR10 and BR11 were more sensitive to water stress than Pajam.

Of the local varieties, Chinigura yielded highest with an average 2.3 t/ha. □

Isozymes, possible markers for blue-green algae (BGA) identification

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To evaluate the potential of electrophoretically detectable isozymes for identifying BGA strains, especially in soil inoculation experiments, we worked to develop a sample preparation method that maximizes zymograms consistency.

The technique is horizontal starch gel electrophoresis using 14% starch in a tris (0.034 M) histidine (0.018 M) gel buffer with pH 8.0 and a tris (0.400 M) citrate (0.105 M) electrode buffer with pH 8.0. Zymograms were revealed by standard specific histochemical staining.

In a preliminary survey, 4 of 18 enzymes were observed in most of the tested strains (20 species in 9 genera) at different growth stages. They were phos-

1. Synthetic diagram of zymograms of various extracts of Anabaena PCC 7120. L = laboratory, P = phytotron, G = greenhouse, T = thawing, G = thawing + manual grinding, S = thawing + sonication.